

THE CONCEPT OF STATE FUNCTION AND ITS ESSENCE**Ashuroxunova Iroda Tohir qizi**

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Annotation: This article discusses the concept of the state, the function of the state, its branches, the procedures for performing these functions, as well as the classification of state functions in jurisprudential theories.

Key words: state, society, state function, state mechanism, internal function, external function, economic function, political function

Analysis of the structure of state-legal phenomena helps their more successful understanding and research. This is especially important when it comes to such a complex and multifaceted phenomenon as the functions of the state.

Category "function" means depend bridge of one object from impact another . And this addition It has certain patterns , knowledge which allows predicting the outcome such an impact and learn its mechanism. As far as law is concerned, it can be said that the function of law reflects the essence of the impact of law on society in general and social relations in particular.

In the literature, there are many interpretation of the concept of "structure". Y. Kerimov understands the structure "internal form (form reflected inward) of a certain object", from this he also deduces two main features of structure. First, the structure cannot have an independent existence. outside the object, the content of which is cemented, organized, ordered by it in a certain way, and, secondly, the nature of its construction and change directly depends on the nature and patterns of development of this object".[1;2]

In his works, S.S. Alekseev identifies regulatory and protective functions rights. Regulatory functions - directions legal action aimed at to ensure proper normal organization of dominant public relations, their statics and dynamics, their functioning in accordance with the requirements objective laws of social development. It is no coincidence that therefore the regulatory functions can be called functions of the organization. [2;1]

Characteristics of structural elements it would be useful to start by defining object, because it depends on the object the subject composition of the implementation of the state function, the nature of their activities and regulatory framework for the implementation of any state function.

The main task of personnel control of the state apparatus as a system of actions is to staffing compliance public body for the planned purposes, requirements of the state personnel policy, in the timely elimination of identified shortcomings and omissions, in increasing the efficiency of civil service employees. In our opinion, personnel control is not an end in itself, control is a process not only of organizational managerial influence, but also of real ensuring a certain content of personnel systems of the state apparatus, search for ways its optimization

It is quite obvious that for the theory of law such a general idea of the functions right is fully justified, which, of course, is not excludes sectoral legal specifics. Each of the branches of law is a complex system with many elements that are interconnected. From the point systems theory view each branch of law as a system has certain patterns of its construction, functioning and development.

Personnel control as a system of measures for the implementation of a certain task should be considered in in combination with other types of control activities. In the state apparatus at the same

time control is carried out through compliance with the law, through the accounting and reporting system, compliance with financial discipline, remuneration, through information support system, etc.

An object is a certain sphere of social relations (economics, politics, culture, finance, etc.), which is directed by state influence. An object serves as the main criterion for distinguishing government functions. At the same time, it should be taken into account that only those spheres of social relations in which there is a state-significant interest can be considered as an object.

Personnel control tool should become set out in legislative and regulatory acts uniform for the entire state apparatus and more stringent professional and qualification requirements for persons occupying government positions of various categories.

Exploring the functions of law, In our opinion, attention should be first of all, on the patterns of interaction of the right system with external objects, since the functions of the system will be expressed in the interconnection of one system with another. Therefore, folding complex bonds between the legal system and the object of legal influence can be defined as functions rights.

When communicating at the household level you hear the word "corruption" in your head thoughts arise about something bad, unkind and insidious. At present, when citizens live in a difficult period of economic transformation in state, world crises, etc., about corruption can and should even be discussed. Moreover, it is necessary not only to speak, but also act. Just voicing the problem of corruption does not solve the problem essentially. Some of us, having spent another public event dedicated to countering corruption, after some time already go to give or take a bribe for a place, per document, per relation and per other good.

Under a state-significant object, in our opinion, one should understand the state interests in a particular sphere of social relations, in the aggregate directed to achieve the goals of the state goals and objectives.

We believe that as a classification criterion for models of state organs should be allocated and legal consciousness. As is known, legal consciousness includes two elements - legal psychology and legal ideology. But if the influence of the dominant ideology in the country on the system state bodies are still being considered, then we are not talking about the feelings, emotions of people about the law. However, reset this factor from the accounts would be wrong. Legal awareness, and especially its second element - psychological, largely determines the mentality of the people, their general spiritual mood.

Each branch of law as a complex system has its own inherent functions, aimed at solving the problems facing the legal system in the field of legal regulation of relevant public relations. Thus, between the legal system and the object on which it acts, line up relevant functional links. To settle relations in any area public life, as a rule, various functions of the legal branch or even functions of various branches of law.

Legal consciousness, depending on the degree of commonality of the subjects they unite, is individual, group and public. Taking into account that the state apparatus is not only a set of state bodies, but also civil servants who carry out in them his labor activity, has meaning to talk about the influence of their group legal consciousness on the formation and functioning of the system of state bodies. Group conscience is part of public legal awareness.

Particular attention is drawn to the process of the emergence and delimitation of objects of state functions. In our opinion, he can happen in two ways. First characterized by the formation of objects of state functions by delimiting spheres of public relations and the creation of specialized state bodies that are subjects of state functions (ministries can serve as a vivid example of such subjects). However With this method, let's conditionally call it pragmatic, the process of the appearance of

objects of state functions is subject to excessive subjectivism, which, in turn, can lead to errors in the selection of objects.

Thus, the model of the state apparatus existing in a particular state cannot but be affected by this factor a. Public legal consciousness largely determines the attitude of the population towards supreme power, its structure, functions, group sense of justice influences to the activities of the state apparatus.

The functions of law have an economic, political and ideological orientation, i.e. one cannot exclude the "presence" of social purpose in the functions rights. But it is not possible to derive directly from it proper-legal functions of law, without losing their legal quality.

Composition, structure, principles of activity of state bodies may depend and from economic factors (according to supporters of the formational approach to the typology of states), and from factors of cultural and historical (civilizational approach). Moreover, in our opinion, it seems superfluous to oppose these factors.

Another way to form objects, as structural elements of state functions, can be conditionally called natural or natural-historical. At In this way, social relations are independently united, due to the natural development of society, into a single group, which forms the object of the state function, and the state for management an already formed object creates special apparatus. However, this method is not without drawbacks.

In the formation of the model of the state apparatus, the dialectical law of the unity and struggle of opposites is reflected, thanks to which, despite obvious differences between subjective and objective, material and spiritual, they are interdependent each other, and their various combination contributes to the evolution of the system of state organs.

It is necessary to point out some signs that characterize the function of law as determined by the social purpose of the main direction of its impact on social relations. The function of law follows from the essence and is determined by the purpose rights in society at a certain stage its development. It represents the direction of its active influence on a particular type of social relationship.

Elements that characterize the form of the state and largely determine the models of the state apparatus, such as the form board, form of government, political regime, are also a combination of objective and subjective beginning.

The state does not always have time to "see" the objects that have matured in society and, as a result, not always manages to create a high-quality subjective apparatus. An example of such a mismatch is the lack of a function to regulate economic development in the USA until the 1920s and 1930s. twentieth century, which led to the Great Depression and forced the US government to impose state control in this area. Drawing an analogy, it is worth thinking about the fact that, perhaps, the economic crisis of the early twenty-first century. caused by insufficiently conscious state influence on the next sphere of social relations.

The problem of choosing for a particular state one or another form of government, state structure and political regime, which determine the model of the state apparatus, is associated with the features development of a particular country, its geographical location, traditional way of life, public conscience.

The functions of law are such a direction of its influence on social relations, the need for the implementation of which gives rise to the need for the implementation of law as a social phenomenon. In this sense, one can say that the function characterizes the direction of the unconditional, necessary impact of law, those. one without which society at a given stage of its development cannot be dispensed with.

The form of the state is not a universal category that allows classifying existing states. However, such classifications are possible if any one structural element of the form of the state (the form government, form of government, or political regime). Each of these elements affects the model of the state apparatus, its structure.

In practice, when forming objects of state functions, synthesis is most acceptable. That is, to determine the object of state-functional influence necessary at an early stage of formation prerequisites for their detection and isolation from the whole complex of social relations. The function expresses the most essential, the main features of law, follows from nature itself and is aimed at the implementation of the fundamental tasks facing law in this stage of its development.

However strict interdependence between all these elements are not observed. So, the republics can be both unitary and federal in the form of state structure, both with democratic and with anti-democratic political regime. It's the same with monarchies. Direct correspondence between the form of state device, form of government and political regime cannot be carried out.

The subject is understood as both the state as a whole and the special bodies created by it that implement this state function, that is, impact on the object. Each state function has its own scope types of government bodies with special competence and created specifically for its implementation.

Terminology (as a collection of terms) state financial control should characterize conceptual relationships knowledge systems reflecting the theoretical understanding of the results of scientific research. Every the term, being an element of the terminological system of state financial control, must have its exact scientific definition in the series its other terms that form the conceptual apparatus of state financial control.

The main functions of law should be considered those of its functions that arise from its essence, are an expression of the social purpose of law as a whole, correspond its main, fundamental tasks and which are inherent in it throughout the entire time of existence research and development, i.e. are permanent for him.

Initially, it was proposed to create a single legal base of the state financial control. To this end, repeated attempts to prepare and adopt an appropriate federal law, which was supposed to define the ideology of the state financial control and establish clear legal mechanisms its implementation.

For example, consider two ministries - education and culture. Being separate state institutions, their activities easily fit within the framework of one state function - ideological, or, as it is also called, the function of developing culture, science and education [3;3].

However, the problem of formation the conceptual apparatus of the state financial control not only did not receive its decision, But, unfortunately, it was made even worse by the fact that in these legislative acts are mixed concepts of state financial control and state audit, as well as differences conflicting and conflicting interpretations of content such fundamental terms as species, forms and methods of financial control.

The functions of law are closely related to its tasks. Tasks are the social problems facing the law, which it is called upon to decide. This is what the right must fulfill now or in the future. In this sense, the task law coincides with its purpose. The right task points to the nearest or the ultimate goal towards which the impact of law is directed. Without implementation functions, none of the tasks can be solved, facing the law [4;4].

It can be assumed that one of the reasons this is the absence in the modern economy theory of generally accepted terminology of finance control, and there is no single position in the literature regarding the definition of these concepts.

In conclusion, in order to determine functions of the state at the level of the subject in as an independent, it is necessary to take into account: permanent or temporary nature worn by state bodies performing a particular function; whether at all levels of government (federal, regional, municipal) they exist; and whether they are duplicative of other functions. However, the main feature that characterizes the subject of a particular function is precisely the special competence.

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